

Grammatical Errors and the Academic Performance of Senior High School Students in Congressional District II, Batangas Province

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Abstract

Grammatical errors continue to be a common concern among students in the Philippines because of differences in language background, limited exposure to English, teaching gaps, and social influences. These errors can affect students' communication skills, comprehension, confidence, and overall academic performance. This study aimed to determine how grammatical errors influence students' academic performance, identify the challenges they experience in developing grammar proficiency, and examine the relationship between grammar proficiency and academic achievement.

The study used a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design. Data were collected from 359 students selected through stratified random sampling using a researcher-made survey questionnaire and supported by unstructured interviews. Statistical tools such as frequency counts, mean scores, and correlation analysis were used to interpret the gathered data and identify significant relationships among the variables.

The findings showed that students frequently commit grammatical errors even though they generally perform above average in both oral and written activities. The results also revealed a significant relationship between grammatical errors, grammar proficiency, and students' academic performance. Many students admitted that difficulties in grammar affect how well they perform in school and limit their confidence in communication.

The study concludes that improving grammar proficiency is important in enhancing students' academic performance, particularly in English. The findings may help teachers develop more focused teaching strategies, improve instructional materials, and provide intervention activities that address common grammatical difficulties. Through these efforts, students may become more confident in expressing themselves and achieve more meaningful learning experiences.

Keywords: *grammatical errors, academic performance, grammar proficiency, English language learning, intervention strategies, language skills*

1. Introduction

Department of Education recognizes English as a vital medium of instruction in the Philippine educational system and as an essential tool for communication in academic, professional, and global contexts. Despite the country's rich linguistic diversity, English remains the primary language used in classrooms and in formal settings such as business meetings and job interviews. However, many Filipino students continue to experience difficulties in mastering the language, particularly in grammar, writing, and speaking. These challenges often limit their ability to comprehend lessons, express ideas clearly, and perform well in subjects that require strong reading and writing skills.

To address this concern, the Department of Education has implemented initiatives to strengthen foundational language competencies and improve the quality of instructional materials. Through stricter guidelines for selecting textbooks and teacher's manuals, DepEd aims to eliminate grammatical inaccuracies in learning resources and promote correct English usage among students. This effort reflects the growing recognition that language proficiency is closely linked to academic success. Studies have shown that students with higher levels of English proficiency tend to achieve better academic outcomes because they are better able to understand complex concepts and communicate their ideas effectively.

Among the different language skills, writing is often considered the most demanding because it requires accuracy in grammar, vocabulary, spelling, and punctuation. Classroom observations indicate that many senior high school students continue to commit frequent grammatical errors in both writing and speaking, particularly in subject-verb agreement, verb tense, and sentence structure. These recurring mistakes may hinder their academic performance and reduce their confidence in using English.

Given the importance of grammar as a foundation for effective communication and academic achievement, this study was conducted to determine how grammatical errors in speaking and writing affect the academic performance of senior high school students. The findings are expected to help teachers design targeted interventions, support school leaders in implementing language development programs, and provide valuable insights for future researchers and policymakers in improving English language instruction.

In the study of Saputra (2022), "Surface Strategy Taxonomy: Error Analysis in Academic Writing," it was found that Indonesian students often struggled with grammar when writing academically. The most common mistakes were omissions, leaving out necessary words and grammatical inaccuracies, using the wrong forms of words, like incorrect verb tenses or word order. Saputra stressed the need to include explicit grammar teaching, regular error correction, and helpful feedback in the learning process.

Similarly, Abdon and Barrios (2024) studied how Tagalog speakers learning English make mistakes with articles like "a," "an," and "the." It was found that many errors happen because learners try to directly translate from Tagalog or get confused about English grammar rules, especially about when to use articles with different kinds of nouns. The most common

problem was adding extra articles where they were not needed. The learners said their mistakes came from translating word-for-word, applying rules too broadly, or not understanding the difference between countable uncountable nouns.

In addition, Comeo (2025) studied the common mistakes made by third-year English pre-service teachers when writing technical texts like letters, reports, emails, and essays. The study found that even though these students are training to be teachers and are expected to be more skilled, they still make many errors, especially with grammar, but also with word choice and mechanics like spelling and punctuation. The research showed frequent problems with verb forms, tense, and subject-verb agreement, as well as mistakes in spelling, punctuation, and capitalization. These errors appeared across all kinds of writing, suggesting that teacher training programs needed to focus more on helping future teachers recognize and fix their mistakes.

Moreover, Alvarez et al. (2024) studied the common writing mistakes made by Grade 6 students. They found that students often make errors with punctuation, capitalization, and verb forms. These kinds of mistakes happened a lot and should be addressed early on to prevent them from becoming permanent habits. The study suggested that teaching materials should focus on these specific problems to help young learners improve their writing skills before the errors become harder to fix.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the frequency of grammatical errors and assess their relationship with the academic performance of Senior High School students in Congressional District II, Batangas Province.

Specifically, this study sought to answer:

1. What is the level of academic performance of the students as assessed by the students themselves through the following activities:
 - 1.1 oral; and
 - 1.2 written?
2. What is the frequency of grammatical errors committed by the students in terms of:
 - 2.1 subject-verb agreement;
 - 2.2 verb tenses;
 - 2.3 preposition misuse; and
 - 2.4 sentence fragmentation?
3. What are the common grammatical errors identified in terms of the above-mentioned variables?
4. What challenges are encountered by the students?
5. What intervention strategies may be proposed to help minimize grammatical errors and enhance students' language proficiency?

The primary objective of this study is to determine the impact of grammatical errors in speaking and writing on the academic performance of senior high school students. Specifically, it aims to identify the most common grammatical errors committed by students in their oral and

written communication, determine their level of academic performance based on their general average, and examine whether a significant relationship exists between the frequency of grammatical errors and their academic achievement. The study also seeks to compare the academic performance of students with varying levels of grammatical accuracy and to develop intervention strategies that may help reduce grammatical errors, strengthen English proficiency, and improve academic outcomes.

Null Hypothesis (H₀): There is no significant relationship between grammatical errors in speaking and writing and the academic performance of senior high school students.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive-correlational research design using a quantitative approach to examine the frequency of grammatical errors, students' academic performance in oral and written activities, and the challenges they encountered in learning English. The participants were 359 Grade 11 and Grade 12 public Senior High School students from ten schools in Congressional District II, Batangas Province, selected through stratified random sampling during the School Year 2025–2026. Data were gathered using a validated researcher-made questionnaire with Likert-scale items that measured the frequency of grammatical errors, academic performance, and perceived learning challenges, supplemented by unstructured interview questions to provide additional qualitative insights. After securing approval from school principals and obtaining informed consent and assent from participants, the questionnaire was administered through Google Forms and printed copies for students with limited internet access. Data collection was conducted over a three-week period in February 2026. The responses were then encoded, organized, and analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, weighted means, and standard deviations, as well as correlation analysis, with the aid of IBM SPSS Statistics.

Results

1. Level of Academic Performance

In this part, the degree or extent of competence and confidence of the students in using English in written and oral activities was measured. This described how well students performed in relation to academic standards.

1.1 Oral Academic Performance

Table 2 presented the indicators of oral academic performance with the composite mean of 2.99 that fell under "Above Average". This demonstrated that respondents have a moderately strong level of oral academic performance in English which meant that students' skills were useful but not in the advanced level.

Table 2
Oral Academic Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can speak in English using correct grammar.	3.11	Above Average	2
2. I can clearly explain my ideas when speaking in English.	2.97	Above Average	6
3. I feel confident answering questions in English during class.	2.87	Above Average	9
4. I can participate actively in English discussions.	3.08	Above Average	3
5. I am confident in my pronunciation of English words.	2.94	Above Average	7.5
6. I can use appropriate vocabulary when speaking in English.	2.94	Above Average	7.5
7. I can respond to questions in complete sentences.	3.01	Above Average	5
8. I can speak in English without frequently switching to my first language.	2.76	Above Average	10
9. I can follow and respond to spoken English instructions.	3.20	Above Average	1
10. I can speak in English with minimal hesitation or pauses.	3.03	Above Average	4
Composite Mean	2.99	Above Average	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = High; 2.50 – 3.49 = Above Average; 1.50 – 2.49 = Below Average; 1.00 – 1.49 = Low

2.2 Written Academic Performance

The table 3 presented the respondent's written academic performance which obtained a composite mean of 3.18, verbally interpreted as "Above Average." This suggested that students saw themselves as competent in doing written English outputs but still needs improvement when it comes to proficiency.

Table 3
Written Academic Performance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can write grammatically correct sentences in English.	3.10	Above Average	8
2. I can organize my ideas clearly in written English tasks.	3.16	Above Average	5
3. I use correct verb tenses in my writing.	3.06	Above Average	10

4. I can apply correct mechanics such as punctuation and spelling in my writing.	3.22	Above Average	3
5. I can use appropriate vocabulary in my written work.	3.14	Above Average	6
6. I can express my thoughts clearly through written English.	3.21	Above Average	4
7. I can complete writing tasks with few grammatical errors.	3.12	Above Average	7
8. I can follow instructions when completing written English activities.	3.30	Above Average	2
9. I can revise and improve my writing when given feedback.	3.38	Above Average	1
10. I feel confident when submitting written English work.	3.08	Above Average	9
Composite Mean	3.18	Above Average	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = High; 2.50 – 3.49 = Above Average; 1.50 – 2.49 = Below Average; 1.00 – 1.49 = Low

2. Frequency of Grammatical Errors

This study determined the frequency of grammatical errors committed by the public SHS students. This part covered four specific types of grammatical errors including Subject-Verb Agreement, Verb Tenses, Preposition Misuse, and Sentence Fragmentation.

2.1 Subject-Verb Agreement

Based on Table 4, the overall composite mean of 2.95, interpreted as Often, suggested that the respondents constantly apply subject-verb agreement in their writing and oral communication tasks. This indicated that students demonstrate a relatively steady awareness of matching subjects with their corresponding verbs in terms of number and tense.

Table 4
Subject-verb Agreement

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can match the subject and verb correctly in simple sentences.	3.25	Often	2.5
2. I know that singular subjects require singular verbs and vice versa.	3.25	Often	2.5
3. I find it difficult to identify the correct verb form when the subject is far from the verb.	2.69	Often	8
4. I double-check my writing for subject-verb agreement errors.	3.36	Often	1

5. I struggle when the subject includes words like "neither," "either," or "each."	2.32	Rare	10
6. I can identify and correct subject-verb agreement errors in other people's writing.	2.97	Often	6
7. I understand how compound subjects (e.g., "my brother and sister") affect the verb form.	3.23	Often	4
8. I make errors with subject-verb agreement in complex sentences.	2.75	Often	7
9. I make subject-verb agreement errors in my writing.	2.64	Often	9
10. I find subject-verb agreement rules easy to remember and apply.	3.04	Often	5
Composite Mean	2.95	Often	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Very Often; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Rare; 1.00 – 1.49 = Very Rare

1.2 Verb Tenses

Table 5 presented the composite mean of 3.10 which is interpreted as Often. This meant that most of the time, students demonstrated the correct usage and awareness of verb tenses and was slightly more competent in using verb tenses compared to subject-verb agreement. Generally, students were able to distinguish and utilize suitable verb tense forms when constructing sentences, mostly in conditions that involves them to describe activities that happened in the different times.

Table 5
Verb Tenses

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can correctly use past, present, and future tenses in writing.	3.40	Often	1
2. I struggle with keeping verb tenses consistent in a paragraph.	2.55	Often	10
3. I understand when to use the past perfect tense (e.g., had eaten).	3.26	Often	4
4. I can recognize incorrect verb tense usage in my writing.	3.11	Often	7
5. I am confident in using simple and continuous tenses.	3.16	Often	6
6. I practice using correct verb tenses when I write stories.	3.24	Often	5
7. I get confused when switching tenses within the same sentence.	2.73	Often	9
8. I find it easy to use future tenses such as	3.34	Often	2

"will" or "going to."			
9. I make fewer tense errors when writing than when speaking.	2.97	Often	8
10. I have improved in using verb tenses through practice and feedback.	3.29	Often	3
Composite Mean	3.10	Often	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = *Very Often*; 2.50 – 3.49 = *Often*; 1.50 – 2.49 = *Rare*; 1.00 – 1.49 = *Very Rare*

1.3 Preposition Misuse

Table 6 presented the difficulties students experienced in terms of prepositions. It has the composite mean of 2.95 which was verbally interpreted as “Often” which meant that challenges in using preposition was common among the respondents.

Table 6
Preposition Misuse

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I get confused when choosing between “in,” “on,” and “at”.	2.63	Often	8
2. I feel confident using prepositions in daily conversation.	3.04	Often	5
3. I have difficulty using prepositions correctly in written English.	2.51	Often	9
4. I understand how prepositions change the meaning of a sentence.	3.20	Often	3
5. I can identify prepositional errors in my writing.	3.03	Often	6
6. I know how to use common prepositional phrases (e.g., in charge of, on time).	3.18	Often	4
7. I know the difference between time and place prepositions.	3.29	Often	2
8. I use unnecessary or wrong prepositions in my sentences.	2.48	Rare	10
9. I want to improve my preposition usage through more examples and practice.	3.47	Often	1
10. I get confused using the right preposition most of the time.	2.70	Often	7
Composite Mean	2.95	Often	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = *Very Often*; 2.50 – 3.49 = *Often*; 1.50 – 2.49 = *Rare*; 1.00 – 1.49 = *Very Rare*

1.4 Sentence Fragmentation

Table 7 illustrated the students' answers about sentence fragmentation. The composite mean of 3.07, verbally interpreted as "Often" showed that problems related to the completeness of sentence composition are regularly experienced by the students as shown through the result of their responses.

Table 7
Sentence Fragmentation

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I can tell when a sentence is incomplete or fragmented.	3.23	Often	3
2. I write sentence fragments by accident.	2.67	Often	10
3. I understand that every complete sentence needs a subject and a verb.	3.38	Often	1
4. I am confident constructing long, complete sentences.	3.08	Often	6
5. I use transitional words (e.g., although, because) without completing the idea.	3.05	Often	7
6. I revise my writing to make sure all sentences are complete.	3.36	Often	2
7. I still struggle to avoid sentence fragments in my compositions.	2.76	Often	9
8. I know how to connect sentence fragments to make complete thoughts.	3.21	Often	4
9. I get corrected by my teachers for using fragments in my writing.	2.77	Often	8
10. I need more practice to avoid writing incomplete sentences.	3.19	Often	5
Composite Mean	3.07	Often	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Very Often; 2.50 – 3.49 = Often; 1.50 – 2.49 = Rare; 1.00 – 1.49 = Very Rare

3. Common Grammatical Errors Identified

The findings revealed that the most common grammatical errors identified among public Senior High School students were related to subject–verb agreement, verb tenses, preposition misuse, and sentence fragmentation. In subject–verb agreement, students often committed errors when the subject was separated from the verb by several words (WM = 2.69) and admitted making subject–verb agreement errors in their writing (WM = 2.64). In verb tenses, students frequently struggled to maintain tense consistency within a paragraph (WM = 2.55), experienced confusion when shifting tenses within the same sentence (WM = 2.73), and continued to make tense-related errors in both speaking and writing (WM = 2.97). In terms of preposition misuse,

students reported difficulty using prepositions correctly in written English (WM = 2.51) and confusion when choosing between common prepositions such as “in,” “on,” and “at” (WM = 2.63). For sentence fragmentation, students acknowledged that they accidentally wrote incomplete sentences (WM = 2.67), struggled to avoid sentence fragments in their compositions (WM = 2.76), and were occasionally corrected by teachers for this type of error (WM = 2.77). Overall, the findings indicated that although students possessed basic knowledge of grammar rules, they continued to experience frequent difficulties applying these rules accurately and consistently in both oral and written communication.

4. Challenges Encountered by the Students in Achieving Language Proficiency

Table 8 showed a composite mean of 3.21 with a verbal interpretation of Agree, which means that students view grammatical efficiency as a vital factor affecting academic performance. This is supported by OECD through its PISA 2025 framework which highlights that literacy involves both written and oral skill that necessitates someone to communicate and apply understanding effectively.

Table 8
Challenges Encountered by the Students

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I believe that having fewer grammatical errors helps me achieve higher grades in my subjects.	3.28	Agree	4
2. I think my performance in English is affected by how well I use correct grammar.	3.26	Agree	5
3. I notice that I perform better academically when I make fewer grammatical errors.	3.16	Agree	6.5
4. I understand that learning grammar rules helps improve my performance in other subjects.	3.53	Strongly Agree	2
5. I find it hard to express my ideas clearly in written tasks because of grammatical errors.	2.88	Agree	8
6. I believe that grammatical accuracy is important in achieving good academic results.	3.49	Agree	3
7. I think frequent grammatical errors lower the quality of my academic outputs (e.g., essays, reports).	3.16	Agree	6.5
8. I experience lower grades when teachers deduct points because of grammatical mistakes.	2.84	Agree	10

9. I believe that improving my grammar will lead to better overall academic performance.	3.59	Strongly Agree	1
10. I find it difficult to understand and learn new lessons effectively because of grammatical errors.	2.86	Agree	9
Composite Mean	3.21	Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

5. Intervention Strategies

Targeted Grammar Enhancement Intervention Strategies for Improving Students' Grammatical Proficiency

I. Rationale

Grammatical errors such as subject-verb agreement problems, incorrect verb tense, misuse of prepositions and sentence fragmentation deliver confusing ideas mainly in written and oral activities, this leads to lower academic performance especially if the activity follows a certain rubrics or mechanics which covers the important components of effective communication.

These difficulties call for the need of a structured intervention strategies that gives attention on enlightening students in terms of understanding and applying grammar rules more effectively through a systematic and contextualized grammar activities. Grammar skills and students' confidence in utilizing the English language will strengthen through the use of module focusing on the common grammatical errors identified in this study, with guided exercises, collaborative learning and continuous practice provided by this program.

II. Objectives

1. Enhance the students' knowledge of fundamental grammar rules in English especially in subject verb agreement, verb tenses, prepositions and sentence construction.
2. Decrease the occurrence of grammatical errors in the students' written output and spoken activities.
3. Develop the ability of students to construct sentences that are clear and free from grammatical errors.
4. Strengthen the students' confidence in utilizing the English language in academic tasks especially in written and oral activities.
5. Support the students' academic performance through honing their skills in writing and speaking.

III. Targeted Participants

- Students who are determined to have frequent problems in grammar accuracy. These are the students within the Congressional District II of Batangas Province who are identified through the conduct of grammar assessment or diagnostic writing and oral activities.

IV. Content/Topics

The intervention program will focus on the following grammar areas:

1. Subject-verb Agreement
2. Preposition Misuse
3. Sentence Fragmentation
4. Verb Tense

V. Expected Output

1. Use of individual progress monitoring records
2. Participate in grammar drills and collaborative activities
3. Completed grammar exercises and short written compositions
4. Corrected outputs showing improved use of grammar.

VI. Expected Outcomes

1. Achieve better academic performance specifically in subjects that involves writing and communication.
2. Improved capability to compose complete and grammatically correct sentences.
3. Enhance understanding of main grammatical concepts that help reduce the occurrence of grammatical errors.
4. Heightened confidence during the use of English language in tasks.

Discussion

- Interpretation of Findings

The findings revealed that public Senior High School students demonstrated an above-average level of academic performance in both oral (composite mean = 2.99) and written English tasks (composite mean = 3.18). Students showed stronger performance in written activities, particularly in revising and improving their work based on feedback, suggesting that they are more comfortable when given time to reflect and edit their outputs. In oral performance, students were most capable of following and responding to spoken instructions, but they still struggled to speak continuously in English without switching to their first language.

The study also found that the four grammatical areas investigated—subject-verb agreement (2.95), verb tenses (3.10), preposition misuse (2.95), and sentence fragmentation (3.07)—were all experienced often, indicating that grammatical difficulties remain common despite students' general awareness of grammar rules. Students demonstrated basic understanding of grammatical concepts, yet they encountered difficulties when applying these rules in complex sentences and spontaneous communication. Furthermore, respondents strongly agreed that improving grammar would lead to better academic performance (composite mean = 3.21), emphasizing their recognition of grammar as an essential component of academic success.

- Comparison to Existing Studies

The results are consistent with previous studies that highlighted the relationship between grammatical competence and academic performance. Dalanon found that students can maintain satisfactory academic performance despite experiencing speaking and grammar difficulties.

Similarly, Tuparan and Caturay Jr. reported that subject-verb agreement, verb tense, and preposition errors frequently appear in students' written outputs.

The findings also support UNESCO (2022), which emphasized the value of oral assessments in measuring real-time language use, and OECD through the PISA 2025 framework, which underscores the importance of literacy and grammar in academic achievement. Other studies by Delos Reyes and Lamela, Bula, and Coidno and Magday similarly found that grammatical errors persist even among students with a foundational understanding of English grammar.

- Implications for Practice and Policy

The findings suggest that grammar instruction should remain a priority in Senior High School education. Teachers should integrate targeted and contextualized activities focusing on subject-verb agreement, verb tense consistency, preposition use, and sentence construction into both speaking and writing tasks. Continuous feedback, guided writing exercises, sentence-combining activities, and collaborative grammar drills can help students strengthen grammatical accuracy and confidence.

At the policy level, schools and curriculum planners may develop structured intervention programs, diagnostic assessments, and cross-curricular language support to address common grammatical difficulties. Since students recognize the importance of grammar to academic success, educational institutions should allocate resources and professional development opportunities to help teachers implement evidence-based grammar instruction strategies across subjects.

- Study Limitations

This study relied primarily on students' self-reported perceptions, which may not fully reflect their actual grammatical performance in authentic writing and speaking tasks. Respondents may have overestimated or underestimated their abilities and frequency of errors. In addition, the study focused only on selected public Senior High School students in Congressional District II of Batangas Province, limiting the generalizability of the findings to other contexts and populations.

The research examined only four categories of grammatical errors—subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, preposition misuse, and sentence fragmentation—excluding other relevant grammatical concerns such as pronoun reference, article usage, and punctuation. Finally, because the study used a descriptive design, it identified patterns and relationships but did not establish causal effects between grammatical proficiency and academic performance.

Conclusion

Summary of Findings

This study focused on the level of academic performance of the students assessed through written and oral activities. Additionally, this looked into the frequency of grammatical errors in terms of subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, preposition misuse and sentence fragmentation. Also, the common grammatical error identified were given focus. Lastly, this study looked into the challenges students encountered in achieving language proficiency.

This study employed quantitative research design utilizing the stratified random sampling which involved the 359 public senior high school students from Congressional District II, Batangas Province during the school year 2025-2026, determined through Raosoft sample size calculator with a 5% margin of error. The data gathering instrument used was a researcher-made questionnaire and unstructured interview questions.

1. Level of Academic Performance

1.1 Oral Academic Performance. Students have moderately strong level of oral academic performance which means their skills are useful but not advanced with a composite mean of 2.99. The highest-ranked statement was following and responding to English instructions with a mean of 3.20 and the lowest-ranked statement was using the English language without first language interference with a mean of 2.76.

1.2 Written Academic Performance. Students admitted that they are competent in writing but still needs improvement when it comes to proficiency with a composite mean of 3.18. The highest-ranked statement was revising and improving their writing upon given feedback with a mean of 3.38 and the lowest-ranked statement was using correct verb tense in writing with a mean of 3.06.

2. Frequency of Grammatical Errors

2.1 Subject-verb Agreement. Students often check their writing for subject-verb agreement errors with the composite mean of 2.95 which means students shows a fairly steady awareness of combining the subjects and their corresponding verbs. The highest-ranked indicator was checking the subject-verb agreement twice with a mean of 3.36 and the lowest-ranked was students' struggle when subject includes distributive words with a mean of 2.32.

2.2 Verb Tenses. Students confirmed that they are often more competent in using verb tenses compared to subject-verb agreement with a composite mean of 3.10. The highest-ranked indicator was utilizing the three basic tenses of the verb correctly with a mean of 3.40 and the lowest-ranked indicator was struggling with keeping verb tenses consistent in longer paragraphs with a mean of 2.55.

2.3 Preposition Misuse. Students often face difficulties in terms of preposition use with a composite mean of 2.95. The highest-ranked statement was improving preposition usage through exercises activities with a mean of 3.47 and the lowest-ranked was using incorrect preposition in a sentence with a mean of 2.48.

2.4 Sentence Fragmentation. Students often experience the problems in terms of sentence completion with a composite mean of 3.07. The highest-ranked statement was knowing

that a complete sentence needs a subject and a verb with a mean of 3.38 and the lowest-ranked statement was writing sentence fragments unintentionally with a mean of 2.67.

3. **Common Grammatical Errors Identified.** Students often struggled with complex agreement rules, maintaining consistent tenses, and correctly using prepositions like in, on, and at, while also occasionally producing incomplete sentences. These errors showed that although learners may understand basic grammar rules, they still face challenges applying them accurately in actual writing, indicating a need for continued practice and support.

4. **Challenges Encountered by the Students in Achieving Language Proficiency.** The composite mean of 3.21 indicated that students see grammatical competence as an important aspect affecting academic performance. The highest indicator was improving grammar leads to better academic performance with a mean of 3.59 and the lowest indicator was experiencing lower grades when students get deduction because of grammatical mistakes with a mean of 2.84.

5. **Intervention Strategy.** This study proposed intervention strategies that intended to provide practice exercises that would help students in achieving grammar proficiency. It was composed of activities focused on subject-verb agreement, verb tenses, preposition misuse and sentence fragmentation.

Recommendations

The study hereby made the following recommendations:

1. Educational organizations may reinforce language instruction by providing learning resources that support the development of students' grammar proficiency.
2. School administrators may implement professional development plans that gives attention on strategies for teaching grammar and advancing students' grammatical accuracy.
3. The intervention activities proposed may be further assessed and considered for implementation by schools.
4. Future researchers may conduct related studies to further examine the approaches that develops students' grammar efficiency.

References

- Abadiano, M. N. & Lacaba, M. M. (2022). *Research Approaches and Designs*. Learning Modules for Research Writing
- Bautista, R., & Del Valle, F. (2023). The impact of oral activities on cognitive development and written communication. *Philippine Journal of Educational Research*, 8(3), 75–89.
- Bula, J. (2024). *Grammatical errors and language competence among Filipino learners*
- Ahmed, S., & Khan, M. (2023). Challenges in English language learning: Grammar, vocabulary, and macro-language skills. *Journal of Applied Linguistics and Language Research*, 10(4), 112–129. <https://jurnal.stkipahsingaraja.ac.id/index.php/tatefl/article/download/648/589>
- Almazan, M., & Aragon, L. (2024). Formal English writing challenges of native Filipino speakers. *International Journal of Contemporary English Studies*, 1(1), 106–120. <https://www.espjournals.org/IJCESA/ijcesa-v1i1p106>
- Benson, C. (2024). *Guidance for the classroom-based assessment of multilingual learners: Assessing languages, literacies and learning across the curriculum*. UNESCO & UNICEF.
- DepEd News. (2025, July 5). *DepEd to use both English, Filipino to teach K–3*. Philippine Star.
- Elimar Alupay Ravina. (2022) Lexical Analysis of Computer Studies Terms Translation from English to Filipino Language. *Journal of Humanities, Arts and Social Science*, 6(1), 113-128.